

Student-parents' Perspectives and Challenges of Online Learning During the Covid-19 Pandemic: A Quantitative Study

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Abstract: The Covid-19 pandemic forced educational institutions to shut down. Just like a damsel in distress, the educational system needed a knight in shining armor, and so online learning comes to the rescue. Online learning rescued many countries from academic freeze during this global pandemic. This present study will explore the perception and challenges of student-parents in online learning during this global pandemic. Perspectives and challenges were also examined in terms gender. Lastly, it is also explored if there is a relationship between the student-parent's perspectives and challenges. Results shows that student-parents have neither positive or negative perception about online learning and that they experience moderate challenges in this learning setup. However, comparing the means between males and females, it is revealed that females are more challenge with this online learning set-up than males with a mean difference of 0.28. In terms of relationship between the student-parents' perspectives and challenges of online learning, the results revealed that respondents' challenges of online learning do not have association with their perspectives.

Keywords: Challenges of Online Learning, Covid-19 Pandemic, Student-parents' Perspectives.

1. INTRODUCTION

The covid-19 pandemic may not be the first pandemic the world has witnessed, not even the first in the 21st century for the first place was taken by SARS in 2012 (Leduc&Barry,2004). But it was the COVID-19 that changed education history forever. In response to the virus outbreak, schools in China, where the Coronavirus started had to shut down and the rest of the world follows. The predicament that this pandemic has caused greatly affected the education system. Education from home was implemented because schools have to close. The education system is like a damsel in distress and online learning came like a knight in shining armor ready to rescue many countries from an academic freeze. However, this new normal setting did not only interrupt the traditional face-to-face learning and teaching system but also caused drawbacks. Students find it difficult to finish their requirements due to distractions and they are not even sure how long they can afford to buy load for internet connectivity because their parents become unemployed during this pandemic (Barrot et al, 2021). With the abrupt transition from traditional face-to-face learning to online learning, teachers, students, and even parents faced many challenges.

Computers may not be new to both learners and teachers but either is prepared for the abrupt transition to online learning. (Hansson,2021). Teachers need adequate support because they have inept experience in using online tools and are often confused as to which resources and methods they can apply to the new mode of teaching. According to the findings of the study conducted by Aytac T. in 2021, aside from the fact that many students are not privileged to have a good internet connection, they are also confronted with technical issues. Students are also having difficulty maintaining their motivation to learn for they are used to a traditional classroom setup, making their homes not conducive for learning. Parents also lack support for the learners. A study conducted by Bhamani et al.(2020) shows that parents are concerned about the challenges such as assisting their children when it comes to technical problems. Additionally, parents have to be more involved in their children's schoolwork because of this new learning setup.

As we have determined earlier review, many research studies have looked at the perspectives and challenges faced by the students, faculty members in higher education, and even the parents during this global pandemic. However, there have not been a lot of studies that give attention to the perception and challenges faced by student-parents during this crisis. This is

the research gap the present study attempts to fill. Revealing the student-parent's challenges and their perception of online learning will provide important data and might help the universities know how to support them. Even before this pandemic started, student-parents are already confronted with problems such as how they are going to manage their time taking care of their family and maintaining their grades. During the pandemic, student-parents should double their time management skill since unlike before when they can play one role at a time; if they are in school their only role is being a student and this will just shift to being a mother or a father if they are at home. This pandemic obliged them to do their dual roles at the same time since the learning is already at home. Thus, this research will explore the perception and challenges of student-parents in online learning during this global pandemic.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Student-parents

Unlike traditional students, student-parents are considered mature students who have parental responsibilities. These students are facing challenges that are unique to them. The literature also suggests that in higher education, this group of students is not given attention and support even though they really need a considerable amount of support. (Miller, 2019; Cruse et al, 2020)

Way back before this pandemic, there are already various challenges faced by student-parents. In the UK context, existing literature highlighted some difficulties student-parents have to confront. These include financial problems, time management difficulties, childcare problems, and managing their roles in their work, family, and study. (Osborne et al; 2004, Brooks 2013; Moreau &Kerner 2015) Similar findings of time management also emerge in Namibia. From the study conducted by Taukeni, S, G. (2014) student mothers also struggled to find time to manage motherhood while studying since domestic chores are always associated with women.

Another challenge and most ignored challenge faced by student parents are health and emotional issues. Moss (2004) noticed that it was always student mothers who have to sacrifice their personal time because of their familial obligations. Given the fact that they are traditionally viewed as the ones who run the house, take care of the family, and do domestic chores they tend to have not enough sleep and end up feeling exhausted. On the other hand, student-fathers are being challenged in providing for their children. Student-parents especially student-fathers are more likely to drop out of college than their female counterparts. (Contreras-Mendez & Cruise, 2021)

2.2 Online Learning Challenges

Online learning refers to a learning setup where students and learners are not in the same setting. It comprises the use of technologies like the world wide web and digital devices to deliver interactive learning to students in the comfort of their homes (Jaradat & Ajlouni, 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic made this the new and necessary way to continue the education system. Flexibility is one of the advantages that online learning boasts. It allows learners to have more control over their learning while doing other obligations such as working or spending time with their family (Richardson &Swan, 2003). For online learning to be effective it is necessary to have plenty of resources and it requires detailed planning (Dhull, & Arora, 2019). This mode of learning, however, is implemented not because the schools and universities wanted to do so but because of the global pandemic, and due to the unexpected transition of learning modality, the world lacked experience in online learning (Zuo et al., 2021) and it has not undergone the same observation as the traditional way of learning (Kenny, 2002; Kozlowski, 2002; Henderson et al., 2002).

In literature, there are already many studies that revealed the challenges associated with online learning. In developing countries teachers, and learners are having a hard time when it comes to access to the internet. It is also much harder for those who are in rural areas (Kanwal & Rehman, 2017 in the Pakistan; Shreedha & Jani,2020 in India and Subedi et al., 2020 in Nepal). Another major problem is the preparedness of the universities to assess learning. (Simbulan, N, 2020.) A study conducted by Aboagye et al. (2021) shows that students are not prepared with the new normal set up which is online learning. Hansson (2021) also found out that trainee teachers have difficulty connecting to the digital environment with their students. Online learning also limits the ways to deliver the content of the lesson because expression and body language are very limited.

Challenges faced by teachers, parents, and even the parents are readily available in the literature. Thus, this paper aims to enrich prior studies by knowing the challenges faced in online learning during this pandemic by those students who are parents at the same time.

3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What are the student-parents' perspectives on online learning?
2. What challenges that student-parents face during online learning?
3. Is there a significant difference between the male and female participants in terms of their challenges in online learning?
4. Is there a significant relationship between student-parents' perspectives and challenges?

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Research Design

This study took survey-based research with a quantitative approach in collecting the data to find out the perspectives and challenges the undergraduate student-parents from different universities face in the online learning set-up during this pandemic.

4.2 Research Instrument

To gather data for this study, a self-administered questionnaire called PCLQ or A Perspectives and challenges of Online Learning Questionnaire developed by Jaradat and Ajlouni from existing literature was adopted. The instrument is composed of 29 items divided into three parts: demographic profile is 5 items, student-parents' perspectives are 8 items, and the challenges student parents face is 16 items. Responses were measured on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly agree).

4.3 Reliability of Instrument

To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pilot testing was administered to a pilot sample of 30 undergraduate student-parents mostly females (29 or 96.8%) with only one male (3.2%) respondent from different universities and will not be part of the final data gathering. In the perspective's subscale, the instrument's reliability is Cronbach Alpha 0.82, and with the challenges' subscale, the reliability is Cronbach Alpha 0.86. The whole instrument yielded the result of Cronbach Alpha 0.81 which shows that the instrument is valid and reliable.

4.4 Respondents

In total, 30 undergraduate student-parents responded to the questionnaire. The majority are females with 83.3% of the total percentage. A total of 46.7% are graduating student parents, 33.3% are third-year students, and first and second-year students are both 10.0% and 66.7 of which have experienced online learning before. In terms of age, the youngest respondent is 18, and 33 is the oldest. The least number of children declared by the respondents is one, while the most are 3 with a mean score of 1.37 (SD- 0.55)

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the respondents (N=30)

Characteristic		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	5	16.7
	Female	25	83.3
Age	18	1	3.3
	19	1	3.3
	20	4	13.3
	21	5	16.7
	22	3	10.0
	24	3	10.0
	25	7	23.3
	26	2	6.7
	28	1	3.3
	29	1	3.3
	31	1	3.3
	33	1	3.3

Year Level	1 st	3	10.0
	2 nd	3	10.0
	3 rd	10	33.3
	4 th	14	46.7
Experience online learning before	Yes	20	66.7
	No	10	33.3
Number of Children	1	20	66.7
	2	9	30.0
	3	1	3.3

Data Analysis:

Responses in student-parents perspectives scale were tabulated and coded. 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly agree. The means were interpreted as follows:

Scale:

4.20-5.0	Positive
3.40-4.19	Somehow positive
2.60-3.39	Neither positive nor negative
1.80- 2.59	Somehow Negative
1.0-1.79	Negative

For the challenges scale, responses were tabulated and coded as follows. 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly agree. The means were interpreted as follows:

4.20-5.0	very high
3.40-4.19	high
2.60-3.39	moderate
1.80- 2.59	low
1.0-1.79	very low

The responses to the questionnaire were set apart. First, the participant's demographics are presented in Table 1 and the three research questions. To answer the first and second research questions, student-parents challenges from items 6-13 and for perspectives from 14-29, items were analyzed using the Statistic Product and Service Solutions to provide descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, and the frequencies and percentages of the responses. For the third research question, an independent sample t-test was used and to determine if there is a significant relationship between the challenges and perspectives, Pearson-r was used.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Student-parents' perception of online learning

Responses to the PCLQ questionnaire were coded and analyzed. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were employed. Table 2 presents the analysis of perspectives data and every item's mean, and percentage are included along with the interpretation (Interpretation: 1.0-1.79 which means negative perception, 1.80- 2.59 somehow negative, 2.60-3.39 neither positive nor negative, 3.40-4.19 somehow positive and 4.20-5.0 interpreted as positive perception).

Table 2: Perspectives of student-parents.

Statements	Response										M	SD	Inter.
	SD		D		N		A		SA				
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%			
1. Online learning is more effective than face-to-face learning	5	16.7	13	43.3	11	36.7	0	0	1	3.3	2.30	0.88	SN
2. Online learning is preferred to face-to-face learning	8	26.7	12	40.0	7	23.3	2	6.7	1	3.3	2.20	1.03	SN
3. Online learning enables the effective exploration of educational materials	5	16.7	12	40.0	7	23.3	4	13.3	2	6.7	2.53	1.13	SN
4. Online learning allows for comfortable electronic communication	1	3.3	6	20.0	14	46.7	8	26.7	1	3.3	3.07	8.86	NP/N
5. Online learning makes it easier to complete group projects and assignments	6	20.0	8	26.7	10	33.3	4	13.3	2	6.7	2.60	1.16	NP/N
6. Online learning saves time for students	0	0	4	13.3	12	40.0	6	20.0	8	26.7	3.60	1.03	SP
7. Online learning enhances knowledge acquisition	4	13.3	9	30.0	15	50.0	2	6.7	0	0	2.50	0.82	NP/P
8. Online learning is perceived as a very useful delivery mode	1	3.3	10	33.3	14	46.7	4	13.3	1	3.3	2.80	0.84	NP/P
Overall Perspective of Student-Parents about Online Learning											2.70	0.53	Neither positive nor negative

Note: N-Number; M-mean; SD-strongly disagree; D-disagree; N-neutral; A-agree, SA-strongly agree

In Table 2, it is shown that the overall mean of the student-parents' perspectives is 2.70 (SD=0.53) with a verbal description of "Neither positive nor negative". The result somehow goes along with the study conducted by Coman et al. (2020) where students are still undecided if they are satisfied with the general online learning environment. However, the present result does not agree with the study conducted by Gherges et al. (2021) with the findings that undergraduates prefer face-to-face learning nor with the findings of Garg (2020), that show students only prefer online learning as a supporting tool and not as a substitute to the traditional face to face learning. The present result may not be in agreement with the previous studies due to the fact that online learning is relatively new to the Philippines and students may be undecided yet about their perception of online learning. 43.3% of the student-parents disagree that online learning is more effective than face-to-face learning. It is no wonder that student-parents still prefer the face-to-face learning set up to online learning as shown in table 2. This could be attributed to the fact that some student-parents may find it hard to juggle their responsibilities at home as a parent and as a student at the same time. Distractions from their child or children can also be a factor why student-parents still prefer the traditional set-up. 40% of student-parents also disclose that exploration of educational material is not effective in an online set-up.

Intriguingly, it could be noted that student-parents somehow agree that online learning saves time for students with the mean score of 3.60 interpreted as somehow positive. It is the only item that received a positive perception in online learning. It is also noted that many student-parents somehow have a positive perception that online learning is a time saver. This may mean that some student-parents can manage their time effectively being a parent and a student at the same time and at the same place. This supports the study of Amir et al.(2020) that students have more time to prepare and review learning materials in an online set-up. However, even though nobody answered strongly disagree in the survey and

the combined percentage of agreeing and strongly agree is 46.7, it can be noticed that 14.3% answered disagree and 40% answered neutrally. The difference between the responses may be related to several factors. First, some student-parents may have difficulty completing group projects and assignments online. In addition, unreliable internet connections may force student-parents to look for a place with better connectivity. Another factor is the number of children a student-parent has. It will be harder for a student-parent to manage time if he or she has more than one child. Another possibility is the item with the lowest mean of 2.50, 50% of the student-parents are undecided whether online learning enhances knowledge acquisition. Student-parents may find it hard to study online materials and have to spend extra hours to figure out the lesson.

Evidently, student-parents are still undecided about their perception. The fact that out of nine items on the perspectives scale four items received neither negative nor positive perception contributed highly to the result.

5.2 Challenges Faced by Student-Parents

To determine the online learning challenges of the respondents, the responses from the PCLQ questionnaire were coded and encoded initially in a spreadsheet. Descriptive statistics were performed to analyze the data presented in Table 3.1. Included in the presentation are the responses in every item of the questionnaire (frequencies and equivalent percentages), mean (M), and interpretation (Interp.) 4.20-5 (very high), 3.40-4.19 (high), 2.60-3.39 (moderate) ,1.80- 2.59 low, 1.0-1.79 very low.

Table 3.1: Challenges of student-parents during an online class.

Statements	Response										M	SD	Inter.
	SD		D		N		A		SA				
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%			
1. Online learning is more expensive than face to-face learning	3	10.0	5	16.7	9	30.0	8	26.7	5	16.7	3.23	1.22	M
2. The internet connection is unreliable	0	0	1	3.3	11	36.7	10	33.3	8	26.7	3.83	0.87	H
3. E-learning platforms and services are slow	1	3.3	4	13.3	11	36.7	10	33.3	4	13.3	3.40	1.00	H
4. Adequate hardware and software for online learning are not available in my house	0	0	11	36.7	9	30.0	7	23.3	3	10.0	3.07	1.01	M
5. I have mental health issues (e.g., anxiety, stress (that affect my online learning)	1	3.3	6	20.0	8	26.7	10	33.3	5	16.7	3.40	1.10	H
6. I am not motivated to learn online	0	0	5	16.7	13	43.3	8	26.7	4	13.3	3.23	1.22	M
7. I cannot focus in an online learning environment and cannot avoid distractions	0	0	4	13.3	6	20.0	11	36.7	9	30.0	3.83	0.87	H
8. I have poor time management skills, which affect my online learning capabilities	0	0	7	23.3	9	30.0	8	26.7	6	20.0	3.40	1.00	H
9. I have poor ICT skills, which affect my online learning.	6	20.0	9	30.0	6	20.0	6	20.0	3	10.0	3.07	1.01	M
10. The technical assistance offered is not adequate	3	10.0	1	3.3	17	56.7	6	20.0	3	10.0	3.40	1.10	H
11. I have technophobia (a fear or dislike of advanced technology),	13	43.3	5	16.7	7	23.3	3	10.0	2	6.7	2.20	1.29	L

which affects my online learning														
12. The isolation of students in online education affects my learning	2	6.7	8	26.7	11	36.7	6	20.0	3	10.0	3.00	1.08	M	
13. The instructor's interaction and feedback are inadequate	1	3.3	6	20.0	10	33.3	10	33.3	3	10.0	3.27	1.01	M	
14. The teaching strategies that are used are not appropriate	1	3.3	9	30.0	13	43.3	4	13.3	3	10.0	2.97	0.99	M	
15. The learning material is poor quality	0	0	11	36.7	14	43.3	4	13.3	2	6.7	2.90	0.88	M	
16. The assessment and evaluation methods are not suitable	1	3.3	10	33.3	14	46.7	3	10.0	2	6.7	2.83	0.91	M	
Overall Challenges Student-Parents experience in Online Learning											3.16	0.64	M	

Note: N-Number; M-mean; SD-strongly disagree; D-disagree; N-neutral; A-agree, SA-strongly agree

Data reveal that of the 16 items in the Challenges Scale, both Item 15 (The internet connection is unreliable) and item 20 (I cannot focus in an online learning environment and cannot avoid distractions) obtained the highest mean of 3.87, followed by Items 16 (E-learning platforms and services are slow), 18 (I have mental health issues), 21 (I have poor time management skills, which affect my online learning capabilities) and 23 (The technical assistance offered is not adequate) with a similar weighted mean of 3.40. With the items that got the highest means, items 15 and 16 suggest that student-parents are 'highly' challenged by unstable internet connectivity. The researcher, as a student-parent herself, knows exactly how disappointing it is that you can't participate well because of the distractions and unreliable internet connection. This is consistent with the previous study of Baticulun et al.,(2021) and Chung et al.(2020) that internet connection is one of the main challenges in an online learning set-up among students. This result suggests that educational institutions should encourage internet providers to increase the bandwidth of internet connectivity. Lack of technical assistance also got a high mean (3.40). This may be due to the fact that learners and teachers are not in the same place and teachers can't offer any assistance if technical problems arise. Another reason behind this is that teachers just like the students may also be experiencing technical difficulties and they may also still be trying to learn how to use the online learning platform. The result can also be due to the fact that the instructor's interaction and feedback are inadequate which gained a mean score of 3.27 which translates to a 'moderate' challenge for the student-parents.

The analysis also revealed that items 27 (The teaching strategies that are used are not appropriate), 28 (The learning material is poor quality), and 29 (The assessment and evaluation methods are not suitable) have moderate interpretations. These items belong to the top five with the lowest means. However, the interpreted means suggest that student-parents are moderately challenged by these items. Student-parents think that lesson materials, and teaching strategies are inappropriate, and evaluation methods are somehow not suitable. These may be due to the unprecedented educational catastrophe. The rapid transition from the traditional learning setup to online learning has caused drawbacks to the faculty members in providing good quality material and to what assessment and evaluation methods they are going to use. This is because there is a difference between well-planned online learning and online learning in response to a pandemic (Hew et al.,2020). The following results support the study conducted by Martin et al. (2019) that faculty members with little to no experience in teaching online have lower perceptions of their online teaching skills, especially technical competence. Paliwal & Singh (2021) also confirm that teachers have inadequate time management skills and technical competency to handle online classes.

It is also interesting to note that item 20 (I cannot focus in an online learning environment and cannot avoid distractions) also got the highest mean of 3.87. The reason seen behind this is that student-parents may have difficulty drawing a line between two important roles they are playing; being a parent and a student, especially if playing both take place in the same physical space. Regarding poor time management, the mean is 3.40 which is interpreted as 'high'. This may be due to the fact that juggling two different roles is really hard. This is similar to the findings of Taukeni (2004) that time management is one of the major challenges of a student-mother. Rajab et al also stated that in an online learning set-up,

time management skill is also one of the challenges faced by learners. Manze et al (2021) also confirm that during this COVID-19 pandemic the already limited time of student-parents is more constrained.

Student-parents also reported that they are moderately challenged by a lack of motivation. (m-3.23) while item 25 with a mean score of 3.0 which is also interpreted as 'moderate' suggests that the feeling of isolation during this online learning somehow challenges them. The reason behind this is that studying alone can be time consuming and these two factors are related. Feeling isolated can somehow reduce students' motivation on learning. According to Rogers (2001), the most important factor in learning is motivation. Therefore, regardless of the learning setup, motivation is really important. So, there is no surprise that in item 18 (I have mental health issues that affect my online learning) 33.3% agreed that they are experiencing mental health issues. The finding about mental health issue is consistent with Fawaz & Samaha (2021) that online learning caused depression and anxiety to undergraduate students. The finding is also in line with the findings of Wu et (2020)al that mental health of student-parents was greatly affected by variety of reasons during this COVID-19 pandemic. Regarding financial issue, item 14 obtained a mean of 3.23 with a verbal description of "moderate" which may result from the need to have internet access. It is also believed that some student-parents are affected to the financial disruptions caused by the pandemic where in many businesses are forcefully shut down. This supports the findings of Rotas & Cahapay(2020) that online learning requires internet expenses and due to the current pandemic, it is hard to look for a job and many lost their jobs.

The item with the lowest mean score (2.20) compared to other items in challenges scale is item 24. The result shows that the combined percentage of agree and strongly agree that they have technophobia is only 16.7 %. 43.3 % answered strongly disagree to the survey, this shows that the student-parents are confident and are engaged in technology. This may due to the fact that learners are now more comfortable in using technology. The result is aligned with the findings of Rajab et al. (2020) that some learners are challenged by technophobia. It is conjectured that students who are experiencing technophobia may also due to the fact that they do not have adequate hardware and software for online learning. Item 17 (adequate hardware and software for online learning are not available in my house) and item 22 (I have poor ICT skills, which affect my online learning) have the same mean of 3.07 which interpreted as a moderate challenge for the respondent. The result means that student-parents lack access to hardware and software that are crucial for this mode of learning. One reason behind this is that schools did not have an orientation on how to navigate the software that both student and teachers will use. To some extent, this finding is consistent with the previous study of Almaiah (2020) that lack of hardware and software is one of the challenges encountered by the learners and that universities must address this issue.

The analysis of the data presented in Table 3 points out that generally, student-parents experience "moderate challenges" in online learning (Mean-3.16, SD-0.64).

5.3 Challenges of online learning across gender

To identify whether there is a statistical difference on male and female respondents' challenges of online learning, the data was treated with the parametric statistical tool known as t-test for independent samples. Table 3.2 gives the independent-samples T-test analysis of the data set.

Table 3.2: Challenges of online learning across gender

Variables		Mean	SD	Sig. (2-tailed)
Dependent	Independent			
Challenges of online learning	Male	2.93	0.70	0.377
	Female	3.21	0.63	

From Table 3, the result shows that there is no significant difference between the challenges experienced by male student-parent from their female counterpart. However, the data revealed that females are more challenge with this online learning set-up than males with a mean difference of 0.28. This may due to the fact that females are traditionally seen as the caretakers of the family and household chores are expected to do by them. Thus, making females more distracted than males. However, it can be noted that the difference is not significant statistically which means that gender is not a factor on the level of challenges faced online. This may due to the fact that both gender needs to stay at home due to the pandemic and gender equality is more practiced and observed in the 21st century.

Correlation: Respondents' Perspectives and Challenges

To determine the relationship between the respondents' perspectives and challenges, the data set was analyzed using a test of relationship, the parametric test known as Pearson Product Moment Coefficient (also known as Pearson r). Table 4 provides the analysis of the data.

Table 4: Relationship among respondents' perspectives and challenges of online learning

Variables		p-value	r-value	Interp.
Perspectives	Challenges	.518	-.123	Not significant

From Table 4, it could be noted that there is no significant relationship between the student-parents' perspectives and challenges of online learning. This means that respondents' challenges of online learning do not have association with their perspectives.

6. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study offer information about the perspectives and challenges of student-parents about the online learning set-up, implemented to carry on the teaching and learning process amidst this pandemic.

The challenges faced by student-parents are both from external and internal factors with a mean score of 3.16 that interprets to a moderate level of challenges. The results suggest that unstable internet connection and the distractions around the house are really challenging and the researcher can really attest how depressing it is to look for a place at home where you can just focus on your studies and activities without distractions especially from children. The prevalence of mental health issue to learners during this pandemic is also present to some of the student-parents. As one of the items that with the highest of all the means in the challenges scale ($m = 3.40$) this suggest that some student-parents need counseling services to address mental and emotional problems such as stress, anxiety and depression especially for student-mothers who faced more challenges. The results should also encourage instructors to assist the learners especially those students with more needs and challenges like the student-parents. Both faculty members and students should also have an orientation on how to navigate software used in delivering online learning, especially that some software are constantly updating. With the 0.27 gathered overall mean for the perspectives scale and with a verbal interpretation of "neither positive or negative" student-parents-are still undecided whether online learning is useful for them during this pandemic.

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